

19 **Abstract:**

20 Many chemicals in day-to-day and industrial usage have ability to cross the blood brain
21 barrier and develop neurotoxicity in human beings. There are numerous *in vitro*, *in vivo*,
22 epidemiological and *in silico* studies developed to test the neurotoxicity of such chemicals.
23 This systematic review summarized the endpoints and biochemical markers generated from
24 *in vitro* models, organism-based models, human studies and *in silico* tools and how they are
25 being used to translate the data for risk assessment of neurotoxic chemicals. With the
26 advancement in experimental studies such as high throughput screening (e.g. proteomics,
27 genomics), there is a huge potential of data generation related to genes and proteins
28 facilitating deep understanding of molecular mechanisms of neurotoxicity. However, this
29 demand a translational platform that can integrate the biological data from different studies
30 mechanistically and thereby translated across intra and interspecies for neurotoxicity
31 assessment. Further, this review proposed an integrative translational framework to assess the
32 chemicals for neurotoxicity.

33 **Keywords:** *in vitro*, *in vivo*, epidemiology, *in silico*, translation, neurotoxicity

34 **Abbreviations:**

BSID:	Bayley Scales of Infant Development	EDCs:	Endocrine Disruptor Compounds
BRIEF:	Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function 2	ROS:	Reactive Oxygen Species
VMWM:	Virtual Water Maze test	NHANES:	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
CNS:	Central Nervous System	EEA:	European Environment Agency
PBPK:	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic Modelling	EU-OSHA:	European Union information agency for occupational safety and health
PD:	Pharmacodynamics	EPA:	Environmental Protection Agency
IVIVE:	<i>In Vitro</i> to <i>In Vivo</i> Extrapolation	WHO:	World Health Organization
QIVIVE:	Quantitative <i>In Vitro</i> to <i>In Vivo</i> Extrapolation	ATSDR:	Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry
SB:	Systems Biology	FRs:	Flame Retardants
GSMN:	Genome Scale Metabolic Network	PFOS:	Perfluoro octane sulfonic acid
QSAR:	Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship	REACH:	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
EFSA:	European Food Safety Authority	PFOA:	Perfluoro octanoic acid
PCBs:	Polychlorinated biphenyls	BPA:	Bisphenol A
LDH:	Lactate Dehydrogenase	LTP:	long-term potentiation
NO:	Nitric Oxide	LTD:	long-term depression
CGMP:	Cyclic Guanosine Monophosphate	POD:	Point of Departure
MTT:	3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide	PFAS:	Polyfluoroalkyl substances
KEs	Key Events	TUNEL:	Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labelling
AOPs	Adverse Outcome Pathways		

36 1. Introduction

37 Chemicals have been produced to serve numerous purposes, starting from its usage in
38 common household items to industrial products. Many of these substances are released in
39 environment and accumulate inside living organisms to harmful concentration (Fonnum and
40 Mariussen 2009). Exposure of these chemicals to living beings have been linked to several
41 adverse outcomes as demonstrated through *in vitro*, *in vivo*, epidemiological and *in silico*
42 studies (Coecke et al. 2006; Asimakopoulos et al. 2016; Tsatsakis et al. 2017). Most of the
43 environmental chemicals are lipophilic in nature and knowledge that they can cross blood
44 brain barrier raise the concern about harmful effect on the nervous system especially leading
45 to neurotoxicity (Weiss 2000; Fonnum and Mariussen 2009; Maffini and Neltner 2015;
46 Philips et al. 2018). Exposure of these chemical in early phase of life might be critical, where
47 the developing human brain undergoes series of changes critically depending on particular
48 sequence of processes occurring at right time and right place (Rice and Barone 2000;
49 Grandjean and Landrigan 2006; Fritsche et al. 2018; Li et al. 2019). There are several
50 regulatory agencies (NHANES, EEA, EPA, EU-OSHA, WHO, ATSDR & EFSA) that keep
51 track of these chemicals related hazardous effects on human health. However, looking into
52 the number of facts for instance; large number of chemicals released into environment,
53 occupational exposure, individual susceptibility, concurrent exposure of multiple chemicals,
54 and complex human nervous system, it is very challenging to apply research finding (*in vitro*,
55 *in vivo*, epidemiology and *in silico* studies) to quantifying the effects of these chemicals on
56 human nervous system (Cowell et al. 2018). To unmet these challenges, the area of integrated
57 translational toxicology has been proposed (Vodovotz et al. 2008; Drolet and Lorenzi 2011;
58 Mumtaz et al. 2012; Hughes et al. 2013; Sedman et al. 2016; Phillips and Bogdanffy 2017).

59 Translational toxicology is a broader concept and different authors define it in different ways.
60 *In vitro* models translate or evaluate toxicological profile of chemicals on human nervous
61 system through different end points, biomarkers and mechanistic pathways (Hartung and
62 Daston 2009; Breznan et al. 2016; Goldberg et al. 2018). *In vivo* has been defined as a field
63 where preclinical findings from animal models are used for assessing behavioral and sensory
64 perturbations and mode of action for better extrapolation to human nervous system (Bruch et
65 al. 2015; Coecke et al. 2006; Huang et al. 2016; Hughes et al. 2013; Kerb et al. 2017).
66 Epidemiological study involves evaluating distribution and determinants of health related
67 events in a specific population to predict the effect of chemicals on humans (Shah et al.
68 2016). Understanding about human nervous system is increasing but still the process of
69 translating fundamental knowledge from *in vitro*, *in vivo* and epidemiological toxicological
70 data to quantification of a toxicity in human is challenging (Bornstein and Licinio 2011;
71 Boberg et al. 2019). As the human brain is a continuously changing organ forming new
72 synapses to store new information and such a way develops a complex network in response to
73 interaction between genetic and environmental factors (Roberts et al. 2015). Also despite
74 similarity in neurodevelopmental processes in mammals, interspecies differences exist
75 leading to species specific features and difference in cognition and behaviour (Silbereis et al.
76 2016).

77 Advances in computational toxicology has led to different *in silico* tools like
78 cheminformatics, toxicokinetics, toxicodynamics, systems biology and toxicogenomics for
79 assessing neuronal risk in different species. Also, need for *in silico* approaches has been
80 suggested by a panel of experts for alternative to experimental testing (Laroche et al. 2018).
81 Different guidelines like REACH, IATA and ITS, focus on integrated analysis of existing
82 information with new information generated from *in silico* tools (Vinken 2019) (Benfenati et
83 al. 2011). Toxicological and biomedical research on nervous system from many decades has

84 led to lot of scientific data which includes information on mechanisms by which
85 neurotoxicants can alter signalling pathways and how such alterations can lead to adverse
86 impact on human biological system (Bal-Price et al. 2017).

87 The main objective of this review was to conduct a systematic search for *in vitro*, *in vivo*,
88 epidemiological and *in silico* studies being conducted in neurotoxicological research and to
89 propose a framework for translational neurotoxicity. To examine the translation in
90 neurotoxicity a systematic study for a specific group of chemicals (FRs, PFOS, PFOA, PCB,
91 BPA and Phthalates) were conducted in this manuscript. In addition, the framework for
92 integrative translation was proposed to transform the results for prediction of neurotoxicity in
93 human species (Figure 1) for risk assessment. This review emphasize how the integration of
94 experimental data (*in vitro*, *in vivo* and epidemiological studies) with *in silico* tools is
95 important to translate the data and also for predicting the adverse effects on human nervous
96 system (Auffray et al. 2003; Vodovotz et al. 2008; Adcock et al. 2010; Drolet and Lorenzi
97 2011; Kerb et al. 2017; Linne 2018). It will also help in understanding the mechanism and
98 long-term effect of neurotoxicants on anatomical, physiological and cognitive functions of
99 nervous system.

100 **2. Methods**

101 **2.1 Data Search**

102 Systematic approach was used for searching database Scopus and PubMed with different
103 keywords as mentioned in SI (Refer Table 1 in annexure). Different search strings were
104 designed to search from these databases in order to identify all the relevant publications for a
105 certain group of chemicals. Research articles from 2006 to Feb 2019 were included in this
106 review. Timespan was used to limit the search results to a reasonable amount. We did not
107 restrict the search by language. Review articles and duplicated studies were overlooked
108 (Figure 1).

109 **2.2 Inclusion Criteria**

110 *In vitro*: We included 2D (e.g. embryonic cell lines), 3D cell lines (e.g. human pluripotent
111 stem cells), cultures and co-cultures. Electrochemical cell chips were excluded.

112 *In vivo*: It includes rats, mice, zebrafish, Marine Medaka, nematodes and *Caenorhabditis*
113 *elegans* (*C. elegans*).

114 Epidemiology: It includes human (pregnant females, males, elderly and children).

115 *In silico*: It includes PBPK, PD, PK, IVIVE, QIVIVE, SB, GSMN and QSAR.

116 **2.3 Chemical Exposure**

117 The exposure of our interest are some of the organic chemicals like flame retardants (FRs),
118 Perfluoro octane sulfonic acid (PFOS), Perfluoro octanoic acid (PFOA), Polychlorinated
119 biphenyls (PCBs), Bisphenol A (BPA) and Phthalates. These chemicals have proven
120 neurotoxic effects. This review will include these neurotoxic chemicals and exclude other
121 chemicals.

122 **2.4 Outcomes**

123 Studies which represent translation of data to assess neurotoxicity by various means like end
124 points, biomarkers, mechanism of action and neurobehavioral assessments were considered

125 for this review. Research of the results was screened for significance in neurotoxicity (Figure
126 1).

127 **2.5 Publication types**

128 Multiple publications based on same study population were considered individually. Articles
129 that do not contain original data like meta-analysis, reviews, conference abstracts were not
130 considered for the study. Studies containing irrelevant population, irrelevant exposure or
131 irrelevant outcome were excluded. Data mining from grey literature was not performed
132 (Figure 1).

133 **2.6 Publications included**

134 For *in vitro*; Out of total articles published, 53 articles were taken for the systematic study
135 after eliminating duplicates and other publication bias. For *in vivo*; 22 articles were included
136 for systematic study. For epidemiology; 15 articles were taken, and for *in silico*, 6 articles
137 were taken for the review.

138 (Figure 1 near here)

139 **3. Results**

140 **3.1 Translational *In vitro***

141 This section focuses on various *in vitro* methods and the approaches that are being used to
142 understand and quantify the chemical induced neuronal toxicity (Refer Table 2 in annexure),
143 hereby we called these as translational approaches. Results are summarized in Figure 2. To
144 discuss the literature finding in a systematic way, we have categorized it as follows: 1)
145 Preliminary screening test i.e. identification and characterization of the neurotoxicants, and 2)
146 Molecular level-screening test i.e. to identify the mechanisms, adverse pathways and end
147 point biomarkers. *In vitro* publications include different endpoints for neurotoxicity as shown
148 in Figure 2 & Figure 3.

149 (Figure 2 near here)

150 Preliminary Screening for neurotoxicity involves cell viability (81.1%), differentiation
151 (18.9%), migration (7.5%) and proliferation (11.3%) (Figure 3). These are key cellular
152 processes critical to neuronal development. *In vitro* cell based cytotoxicity assays like LDH,
153 MTT assay and high content analysis approach is used for quantification of neurites to
154 measure cell viability (Wilson et al. 2014). Out of 53 articles, 43 articles included cell
155 viability as the test for neurotoxicity (Reistad et al. 2006; Lyng et al. 2007; Yoot et al. 2007;
156 Costa et al. 2007, 2016; Giordano et al. 2008; Le et al. 2008; Slotkin et al. 2008, 2017;
157 Dingemans et al. 2009; Giordano et al. 2009; Götz et al. 2009; Ndountse and Chan 2009;
158 Rodrigo et al. 2009; Fan et al. 2010; Tagliaferri et al., 2010; Dishaw et al. 2011; Tofighi et al.
159 2011; Chen et al. 2011, 2017; Al-Mousa and Michelangeli 2012; Ziemińska et al. 2012;
160 Fanelli et al. 2012; Jiang et al. 2012; Hendriks et al. 2012, 2014; T. Li et al., 2013; Gassmann
161 et al. 2014; Ishido and Suzuki 2014; Xu et al. 2014; Wu et al. 2014, 2016; Yin et al. 2015,
162 2018b, 2018a; Szychowski and Wójtowicz 2016; Hirsch et al. 2017; Li et al. 2017; Sethi et
163 al. 2017; Canzoniero et al. 2017; Cho et al. 2018; Sirenko et al. 2019; Wójtowicz et al. 2019).
164 In ten articles, authors have measured neurite outgrowth to check the neuronal differentiation
165 (Tofighi et al. 2011; Chen et al. 2011, 2017; T. Li et al., 2013; Wu et al. 2014; Xu et al. 2014;

166 Yin et al. 2015, 2018a, 2018b; Sethi et al. 2017). Various authors have observed cell
167 migration in different cell culture like neural crest cell (Hirsch et al. 2017), stem cells (Ishido
168 and Suzuki 2014), human neural progenitor cell (Götz et al. 2009) and hippocampal neuron
169 glial co-culture (Sethi et al. 2017). Cell proliferation has also been studied as the marker of
170 neurotoxicity (Costa et al. 2007; Götz et al. 2009; Li et al., 2013; Ishido and Suzuki 2014;
171 Tofighi et al. 2011; Wu et al. 2016).

172 Molecular level screening comprises of the mechanism of action, cellular and molecular
173 pathway responsible for causing change in neuronal cell through functional toxicity assays.
174 Oxidative stress (39.6%) and signalling pathways (7.5%) (Figure 2) are being extensively
175 studied through *in vitro* models and considered important key events (KEs) (Bal-Price et al.
176 2015). Neurons have high glucose metabolic demand which make oxidative stress as one of
177 key factor leading to neuronal cell death (Gartlon et al. 2006). Increase in ROS (Reistad et al.
178 2006; Giordano et al. 2008; Tagliaferri et al., 2010; Liu et al. 2011; Al-Mousa and
179 Michelangeli 2012; Ziemińska et al. 2012; Jiang et al. 2012; Hendriks et al. 2012, 2014; Wu
180 et al. 2014; Costa et al. 2016; Cho et al. 2018; Yin et al. 2018b, 2018a; Wójtowicz et al.
181 2019), change in mitochondrial membrane permeability (MMP) (Al-Mousa and Michelangeli
182 2012; Ziemińska et al. 2012; Sirenko et al. 2019), ATP levels (Hirsch et al. 2017), lipid
183 peroxidation (Giordano et al. 2008; Slotkin et al. 2008; Tagliaferri et al., 2010; Costa et al.
184 2016) and GSH levels (Lyng and Seegal 2008; Giordano et al. 2008, 2009) are mechanistic
185 endpoints (Figure 3) being studied which cause oxidative stress (Gartlon et al. 2006). Also,
186 NO CGMP pathway; lead to hippocampal LTP and LTD impairing learning capabilities
187 (Rodrigo et al. 2009; Chen et al. 2018), NOTCH and WNT signalling pathway; affect HES1
188 & HES5 which results in delayed neurogenesis (Tofighi et al. 2011) and phosphorylated
189 extracellular signal-regulated kinase (Perk)1/2 pathway; for neuronal impairment (Fan et al.
190 2010) has been extensively reported as the end point for human nervous system toxicity.

191 Increasing evidence with time support the utility of certain biomarkers (90.6%) like alteration
192 in protein levels (Lyng et al. 2007; Ndountse and Chan 2009; Chen et al. 2011; Dishaw et al.
193 2011; Al-Mousa and Michelangeli 2012; Fanelli et al. 2012; Jiang et al. 2012; T. Li et al.,
194 2013; Canzoniero et al. 2017; Slotkin et al. 2017; Cho et al. 2018; Sethi et al. 2018; Yin et al.
195 2018a), neurotransmitters including GABA and glutamate (Lyng and Seegal 2008; Giordano
196 et al. 2008; Dingemans et al. 2009; Costa et al. 2016; Chen et al. 2018), synaptic markers
197 (Fanelli et al. 2012; Lesiak et al. 2014) and change in enzymatic activity (Reistad et al. 2006;
198 Slotkin et al. 2008; Dishaw et al. 2011; Wójtowicz et al. 2019) as indicators of neuronal
199 damages and important key events for AOPs (Bal-Price et al. 2015; Roberts et al. 2015).
200 Neurotoxicity of a chemical can be often determined by presence of particular membrane
201 receptors (Ndountse and Chan 2009; Lesiak et al. 2014; Chen et al. 2017; Sethi et al. 2018)
202 and gene expression (Chen et al. 2011; Dishaw et al. 2011; Warita et al. 2013; Lesiak et al.
203 2014; Sirenko et al. 2019) which affect the molecular target/pathways. Calcium Homeostasis
204 has a pivotal role in inter and intra neuronal processes like neurodevelopment, neuronal
205 function, gene transcription (Carrasco and Hidalgo 2006), neurotransmission (Westerink
206 2008), neurodegeneration and dopaminergic cell survival. Changes in calcium (Reistad et al.
207 2006; Dingemans et al. 2009; Götz et al. 2009; Rodrigo et al. 2009; Liu et al. 2011; Tofighi et

208 al. 2011; Al-Mousa and Michelangeli 2012; Ziemińska et al. 2012; Langeveld et al. 2012;
209 Hendriks et al. 2012, 2014; Gassmann et al. 2014; Costa et al. 2016; Yin et al. 2018a; Sirenko
210 et al. 2019) is considered an important KEs. Different end-points and biomarkers from *in*
211 *vitro* neurotoxicity were identified as common KEs with high predictivity for neuronal
212 damage. AOPs development for neurotoxicity are one-step forward for translation of results
213 to human species. Further, data is needed to demonstrate and validate the results properly.

214 (Figure 3 near here)

215 **3.2 Translational *In vivo***

216 This section will encompass various *in vivo* tests and the translational approaches to
217 understand and quantify the chemical induced neuronal toxicity (Figure 4) (Refer Table 3 in
218 annexure). Here we will be discussing neurobehavioral assays (phenotypic biomarkers),
219 histopathology test and identification of cellular and molecular biomarkers (Figure 5).

220 (Figure 4 near here)

221 *In vivo* models like zebrafish, nematodes, *Caenorhabditis elegans*, rats and mice have been
222 used to evaluate neuronal behaviour after chemical exposure (van der Merwe et al. 2019).
223 These models offer chemical safety reference and are one-step closer to translate the effects
224 on human nervous system. Mostly neurobehavioral assessment (63.6%) have been used as a
225 close proxy to check neurological disturbances or damage (Figure 5) (Dingemans et al. 2007;
226 Vitalone et al. 2008; Boix et al. 2010; Kim and Pessah 2011; Tseng et al. 2013; Lee et al.
227 2014; Ma et al. 2015; Moser et al. 2015; Liu et al. 2018; Yang et al. 2018; Zhang et al. 2018,
228 2016; Zhu et al. 2018).

229 Neuroscientists conduct basic tests in animals to detect changes in brain morphology which
230 includes phenotypic characters such as organ weight and growth (18.2%) (Malkiewicz et al.
231 2006; Moser et al. 2015; Vitalone et al. 2008; Yang et al. 2018), histopathological study
232 (18.2%) (Ma et al. 2015; Liu et al. 2018; Yang et al. 2018; Zhang et al. 2018) and target
233 tissue concentration of chemical (13.6%) (Vitalone et al. 2008; Ruan et al. 2009; Lee et al.
234 2014). Hormonal activities e.g. thyroid hormones play an important role in brain growth
235 during foetal and early phase of life. Unbalances in these hormones level has an impact on
236 brain development, cell number, cell migration and synaptogenesis as studied by Moser et al.
237 (2015), Wang et al (2015) and Zhu et al (2018). Cell death research in recent years has led to
238 development of certain gold techniques like TUNEL and other mechanisms for identifying
239 neuronal cell death (9.1%) (Yang and Lein 2010; Zhang et al. 2018) (Figure 5).

240 Concerning to the effect of chemicals on nervous system, some authors have explored the
241 principal mechanism behind neurotoxicity through different biomarkers (81.8%) (Figure 5).
242 Firstly, neurotransmission as an important mechanism how neuron conducts message and the
243 impact on this can be known by measuring neurotransmitters as a biomarker (Boix et al.
244 2010; Dingemans et al. 2007; Gee et al. 2011; Lei et al. 2017; Moser et al. 2015; Pham-Lake
245 et al. 2017; Wang et al. 2015; Zhang et al. 2018; Zhu et al. 2018). Secondly, neurochannels
246 balance ionic concentration inside and outside of the cell through voltage gated calcium
247 channels and calcium could be a biomarker to study the ion channel mechanism (Mochida
248 2000; Dingemans et al. 2007). Altered neurotransmitters like GABA, glutamate and
249 dopamine can cause impairment in frontal cortex thereby affecting learning and memory
250 (Bradner et al. 2013). Also, ROS (13.6%) production due to oxidative stress leads to effect on

251 nervous system (Tseng et al. 2013; Ma et al. 2015; Wang et al. 2015). Lately, advancement is
252 being made in recognizing the patterns of response in genes (transcriptome) (Basha et al.
253 2006; Malkiewicz et al. 2006; Tseng et al. 2013; Wang et al. 2015; Liu et al. 2018; Yang et al.
254 2018; Zhang et al. 2018; Zhu et al. 2018) and proteins (proteomics) (Basha et al. 2006;
255 Malkiewicz et al. 2006; Dingemans et al. 2007; Boix et al. 2010; Yang and Lein 2010; Morris
256 et al. 2012; Lee et al. 2014; Ma et al. 2015; Wang et al. 2015; Lei et al. 2017) that might be
257 predictive of neuronal effects. Study on effect of immune cells (4.5%) on nervous system
258 measuring subsets of T cells from spleen, myelin basic protein level, serum markers and T
259 cells infiltration in brain region has evaluated by Morris et al. (2012) (Figure 5).

260 (Figure 5 near here)

261 **3.3 Translational Epidemiology**

262 This section includes epidemiology studies and the translational approaches to understand the
263 chemical induced neuronal toxicity (Figure 6) (Refer Table 4 in annexure). Here we will be
264 discussing neurobehavioral assays based scoring, questionnaire survey, biomonitoring assays
265 and statistical tools to interpret the results for the risk assessment (Figure 7).

266 (Figure 6 near here)

267 Epidemiological studies are widely recognised and different authors have estimated the
268 neuronal risk via statistical analysis of various endpoints and exposure assessment (Chiu
269 2017). Studies confirm the complex interaction between neurodevelopmental changes and
270 exposure to environmental toxicants (Al Aïn et al. 2017). Neurobehavioral assessment is for
271 providing insight into functional integrity of brain and predictive of neurodevelopment of
272 different brain regions (Craciunoiu and Holsti 2017; Eeles et al. 2017). Out of fifteen articles,
273 thirteen studies evaluated the performance through neurobehavioral assessment (86.7%) to
274 analyse the development of brain (Park et al. 2010; Chen et al. 2013, 2016; Adgent et al.
275 2014; Bellinger et al. 2016; Shin et al. 2016; Goudarzi et al. 2016; Braun et al. 2017; Doherty
276 et al. 2017; Gaum et al. 2017; Shrestha et al. 2017; Vuong et al. 2018a, 2018b). These
277 assessments evaluated various aspects like reading abilities, intelligence, behaviour, cognitive
278 and motor skills to develop a causal link between chemical exposure and development of
279 human brain. Exposure to general population has been studied by all the authors (100%)
280 measuring the concentration of chemicals in serum, breast milk, blood, cerebrospinal fluid,
281 lipid and urine in pregnant female, foetus, children and adults (Park et al. 2010; Chen et al.
282 2013, 2016; Adgent et al. 2014; Bellinger et al. 2016; Shin et al. 2016; Goudarzi et al. 2016;
283 Lien et al. 2016; Braun et al. 2017; Doherty et al. 2017; Gaum et al. 2017; Shrestha et al.
284 2017; Vinceti et al. 2017; Vuong et al. 2018a, 2018b). Goudarzi et al. (2016) have done a
285 self-administered questionnaire survey (6.7%) to understand information about smoking,
286 weight, economic status and other social factors to observe impact on human nervous system.

287 Different kind of regression models were applied to evaluate the effect of explanatory
288 variables like exposure, risk factor etc. on the response variable (neuronal damage,
289 development of nervous system) (Park et al. 2010; Chen et al. 2013, 2016; Adgent et al.
290 2014; Bellinger et al. 2016; Goudarzi et al. 2016; Braun et al. 2017; Doherty et al. 2017;

291 Gaum et al. 2017; Vinceti et al. 2017; Vuong et al. 2018). Goudarzi et al. (2016) & Shin et al.
292 (2016) used Spearman rank correlation coefficient, the Mann–Whitney U-test, and the
293 Kruskal–Wallis test to analyse the correlation between chemical concentration and BSIDII
294 scores individually with participant’s characteristics. For accommodating multiple
295 comparison Hsu-Dunnet method was used to compare the least square means of BSIDII
296 (Goudarzi et al. 2016). Vuong et al. (2018) applied multiple informant model to generate odd
297 ratio and confidence intervals to analyze correlation between In-transformed childhood PFAS
298 concentration and BRIEF score. Bellinger et al. (2016) calculated Pearson correlation
299 coefficient between log 10 creatinine standardized urinary phthalate metabolite and then used
300 a linear mixed model to estimate the difference in VMWM performance between girls and
301 boys. Authors are able to translate the data from epidemiological studies using end-points and
302 statistical tools and come up with conclusions but still criticism lies where study on larger
303 scale is required or sometimes researchers are unable to come up with a clear conclusion.

304 (Figure 7 near here)

305 **3.4 Translational *In silico***

306
307 With advancement in computational modelling, different *in silico* tools are available to assess
308 the potential of chemicals to initiate adverse effects on nervous system based on structure,
309 physicochemical and biological properties. The examples include cheminformatics model
310 like Quantitative Structure Activity relationship (QSAR) and structure activity relationship
311 (SAR) for predicting activity of compound based on structure. Also, toxicokinetics,
312 toxicodynamic and toxicogenomic models like PBPK, IVIVE, QIVIVE, PD, SB and GSMN
313 are available to determine concentration range relevant to realistic exposure and extrapolation
314 of health risk for chemicals on human species from *in vitro* and other species (Coecke et al.
315 2006; Gartlon et al. 2006; Li et al. 2019).

316 Search was conducted with different keywords (Refer Table 1 in annexure) to see *in silico*
317 tools for neurotoxicity but only 6 articles were found (Refer Table 5 in annexure). In four
318 articles, QSAR with *in vitro* data was used to investigate the neurotoxicity (Rayne and Forest
319 2010; Stenberg et al. 2011; Holland et al. 2017; Pradeep et al. 2019). Stenberg et al. (2011)
320 used *in vitro* screening coupled with QSAR to investigate the toxicity and classify PCBs in
321 two groups based on structure activity relationship and toxicity. They used QSAR modelling
322 to recognize the chemical properties, which can describe potency of non-dioxin like PCBs,
323 and to predict the activities of different congeners of PCBs on nervous system. Holland et al.
324 (2017) assessed the ryanodine receptor activity of 14 untested PCB congeners for evaluating
325 QSAR predictability. *In vitro* assay was done to support QSAR findings. In another article
326 by Gascon et al (2013), epidemiology study was performed to validate PBPK model. They
327 conducted epidemiological study to evaluate neurotoxicity of persistent organic pollutant in
328 Spanish children through breastfeeding exposure to validate the results from PBPK model
329 for postnatal exposure assessment. In addition, Sharma et al. (2017) showed one example of
330 integrated approach. Authors used PBPK/PD model to understand dynamics and steady state
331 behavior of cellular response under perturbed condition. They developed PBPK/PD coupled
332 transduction signalling linking miRNA- mRNA-BDNF-cell survivability to evaluate the

333 PFOS induced neurotoxicity. Authors shown BDNF as a biomarker linking environmental
334 exposure and neuronal adverse outcomes and taken *in vitro* data to assess neuronal cell
335 survivability.

336 **4. Integrated approach for Translating data**

337 Regulatory authorities across the world have made considerable progress towards developing
338 pragmatic frameworks to deal with combined exposure for chemicals to assess risk. The
339 National Research Council (NRC) of the National Academies of Science published a report
340 of its vision of toxicity testing in the 21st century proposing the current toxicity testing
341 paradigm that depends upon whole-animal tests to be replaced with a strategy based upon *in*
342 *vitro* tests, *in silico* models and evaluations of toxicity at the human population level
343 (Bushnell et al. 2010). Programmes like Integrated testing strategy (ITS) and Integrated
344 Approach to Testing and Assessment (IATA) focus on combining information from testing
345 and non-testing methods and aims on prioritizing chemicals using hypothesis (Tollefsen et al.
346 2014; Vinken 2019). REACH guidelines accept *in silico/in chemico/in vitro* tools for skin
347 sensitization prediction apart from *in vivo* and further propose integrated strategy (European
348 Chemicals Agency 2006). This is a strong proof that *in silico* methods can be used for
349 toxicity prediction and are future of the toxicity testing.

350 Current *in silico* models are QSAR, toxicokinetic, pharmacodynamics, systems biology and
351 genome scale models. QSAR are first level models for predicting the activity of compound
352 based on structure, which can be used for screening of thousands of chemicals. Rayne and
353 Forest 2010 and Pradeep et al. 2019 used QSAR to screen PCBs and further used *in vitro* data
354 for validation. Second level are toxicokinetics models which take information on absorption,
355 distribution, metabolism and excretion, therefore can be used to understand concentration of
356 particular chemical in different organs and also to extrapolate dose taking into account
357 biological differences (Martínez et al. 2018; Sharma et al. 2018). Ramoju et al. 2017
358 developed PBPK model for estimating manganese (Mn) concentration in different parts of
359 human brain through different routes. They used exposure data from eight epidemiological
360 studies and in conjunction with severity scores, a tissue dose response relationship was
361 developed. Croom et al. 2015 used *in vitro* data and PBPK modelling to perform IVIVE for
362 Lindane neurotoxicity in humans. Third level is pharmacodynamic and systems biology model
363 which can use data from toxicokinetics and experiments to further understand mechanistic
364 approach and toxicity pathways at molecular and cellular level. Kolodkin et al 2019 applied
365 ROS model with altered proteins and antioxidants levels for disease like Parkinson. Audouze
366 et al. 2018 developed a network based model by integrative systems biology approach to
367 examine the developmental neurotoxicity by larvicidal pyriproxifen. Last and advanced stage
368 is toxicogenomics (genome scale model) for utilizing gene expression which is a step forward
369 for proactive predictive, personalized and preventive toxicology (P4). GSMN models are still
370 not available widely for brain specific pathologies but with increased omics data, there lies an
371 opportunity for computational investigation of brain networks (Sertbas and Ulgen 2018).

372 Objective of our manuscript was to propose an integrative translational framework where
373 collected data and all information available can be coupled to predict the neuronal adverse

374 effects. We propose a framework that incorporate the four levels of *in silico* model gene
375 specific functions (GSMN), molecular & cellular mechanism (SB & PD), quantitative kinetic
376 modelling (PBPK, QIVIVE) and QSAR along with experimental data for different organs
377 and exposure scenario to understand neuronal homeostasis, plasticity, learning and
378 neurotoxicity (Figure 8). Such approach can be used to study dynamical function of brain at
379 various levels and explore mechanistic pathways for both healthy and unhealthy nervous
380 system. This can provide clear picture about nervous system function and adverse outcome
381 pathways (Geschwind and Konopka 2009). With lots of data available (*in vitro*, *in vivo*,
382 epidemiology, genetic, transcriptomic, metabolomics, proteomic), *in silico* models can be
383 validated and integrated for future hazard and risk assessment in Neurotoxicology (Figure 8).

384 (Figure 8 near here)

385 **5. Discussion & path forward**

386 Translating the data for chemicals through *in vitro*, *in vivo*, epidemiology and *in silico* studies
387 is very critical for human risk assessment. This review was to broadly understand how
388 authors are translating the data in neuroscience to predict toxicity and discuss about the
389 integrated approach for neurotoxicology. Research has yielded a lot of scientific literature on
390 neurotoxicity, which contains information about various chemicals, mechanism by which
391 chemicals affect neuronal development and toxicity pathways. *In vitro* studies are conducted
392 from a long time and traditional cytotoxicity test is considered as early markers for neuronal
393 damage. Other tests like oxidative stress, biomarkers and pathways are common in both
394 animal model and *in vitro* studies. Various authors have indicated involvement of oxidative
395 stress (ROS) in a number of neurodegenerative states due to neurotoxic chemicals. ROS is
396 widely known to damage bio macromolecules like lipid, proteins, sugar and polynucleotides
397 and lead to formation of secondary products which are as much damaging as the initial ROS
398 (Sayre et al. 2008). Both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies check the ROS formation as indicator
399 for neurotoxicity. Different biomarkers has been studied in animals and *in vitro* models to
400 observe physiological and morphological changes in neuronal cells and tissues resulting from
401 chemical exposure (Roberts et al. 2015). This indicates that *in vivo* studies can be replaced by
402 *in vitro* model for checking chemical induced neurotoxicity.

403 Behavioural alterations from *in vivo* studies and mechanistic pathways from *in vitro* models
404 demonstrate that neurotoxic chemicals may impair neural development, synaptic plasticity
405 and brain organ growth. However, are these studies enough for human risk assessment taking
406 into account these are indirect measures of neuronal damage and are dose dependent? Are we
407 extrapolating dose correctly from *in vivo* animal studies to humans based on anatomical and
408 physiological differences? Such findings arise the awareness for necessity of human exposure
409 assessment for further confirmation of the risk. Epidemiological studies are conducted for
410 selected neurotoxicants. These studies have investigated the causal association between
411 chemical exposure and neurobehavioral assessment through significant statistical tools. In
412 epidemiology, most of the time exposure effect is assessed by observational data and there is
413 a possibility that exposure response association may be biased. Nevertheless, large sample
414 size, multiple end-points and further investigation is needed to get the confidence for

415 neuronal damages. Also, signs and symptoms in the human brain tend to be non-specific and
416 variable upon environment and exposure (Grandjean et al. 1996).

417 The fact that a particular chemical is causing neurotoxicity is not enough for risk assessment.
418 As we are being exposed to a number of chemicals every day, chronic toxicity evaluation for
419 each chemical to set reference dose and regulatory limits like daily acceptable intake,
420 occupational exposure limit and derived no-effect level using *in vivo* study is not feasible
421 (Tsatsakis et al. 2016). Human real life scenario for chemical exposure is totally different
422 due to low dose exposure of chemicals for humans and mixture of chemicals (Tsatsakis et al.
423 2019). It is not feasible to conduct epidemiological studies for testing every chemicals in
424 human biological fluids. Recognising the need for a paradigm shift of current approaches to
425 risk assessment, regulatory guidelines have changed. Regulatory toxicology is shifting from
426 decision making based on animal models to biological pathway, *in silico* and mechanistic
427 approaches that lead to the understanding of cellular, molecular, organism and population
428 based dynamics. A key driver for this change is computational tools and the *in vitro* studies
429 that are less time consuming and cost efficient for toxicity prediction (NRC 2007).

430 Authors have used *in silico* tools like cheminformatics and toxicokinetics models with
431 available experimental data to validate their results. QSAR has been widely used to screen
432 chemicals and determine priority in which they need to be tested (Holland et al. 2017;
433 Stenberg et al. 2011). With *in vitro* and *in vivo* data available for validation of these QSAR
434 findings, the limitations of QSAR approach can be improved. PBPK model along with *in*
435 *vitro* and epidemiological data was used for predicting effect of chemicals on brain (Gascon
436 et al. 2013; Sharma et al. 2017). Toxicodynamics and toxicogenomic models are rare for
437 neurotoxicity for selected group of chemicals. Very few articles for brain *in silico* modelling
438 raises obvious question. Are we utilizing the available data properly to assess the human
439 nervous system risk? Is there a need for integrated testing strategy or a framework for risk
440 assessment? The answer is that *in silico*, models can be used as stepwise strategy for
441 screening of chemicals. These computational models can utilize different datasets (*in vitro*, *in*
442 *vitro* and epidemiological) for validation and prediction of risk (Figure 1). *In vitro* data can
443 provide mechanistic understanding and *in vivo* data for pathways and better understanding on
444 neuronal damage. Epidemiology studies gives clear understanding about adverse effects in
445 humans and different levels of *in silico* model can be used above data in a fruitful manner to
446 predict the neurotoxicity. The proposed integrated framework utilizing all available data in a
447 constructive manner will help in screening thousands of chemicals with less effort and
448 reduced cost. This integrated framework requires collaborative efforts from different fields to
449 validate and evaluate the performance to assess human risk from neurotoxic chemicals.
450 However, some gaps exist in this framework like dose variation in animal, human and *in vitro*
451 studies, species to species variation, extrapolation of results from adult to mother and
452 children, human brain complexity, etc. Nevertheless, further research on computational
453 models and integrated framework will make them more robust and strengthen the confidence.
454 Then, it may be possible to conduct human risk assessment of specific chemical classes with
455 more clear and precise data. Therefore, the integrated translational framework must be tested
456 with different set of chemicals for assessing its performance and detecting the gaps.

457 **6. Conclusion**

458 After reviewing all the endpoints, biomarkers and pathways used for translation through *in*
459 *vitro*, *in vivo*, epidemiological and *in silico* studies, it provides a clear picture of extensive
460 datasets available with us. In addition, it provides idea of different tests being used for
461 assessing neurotoxicity of chemicals. The proposed integrated approach utilizes the available
462 experimental dataset along with *in silico* model for neurotoxic chemicals. This integrated
463 approach can be used for screening and evaluating the toxicity of thousands of neurotoxic
464 chemicals.

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472 **Declaration of interest**

473 All authors declare they have no potential competing financial interests.

474 **Supplementary**

475 Please find attached supplement file: Annexure 1 Tables

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970 **Figures**
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973 **Figure 1:** Diagram summarizing the research from pilot systematic review. It includes total
 974 articles searched using different database and keywords, reasons for excluding the articles
 975 and total number of review articles included for this systematic review.

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978 **Figure 2:** Diagram represents percentage distribution of various tests performed *in vitro* for
 979 inspecting the influence of chemicals on nervous system. Primary tests include cell viability,
 980 differentiation, migration and proliferation. Molecular level tests comprises of oxidative
 981 stress, pathways and biomarkers for assessing neurotoxicity by different chemicals.

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984 **Figure 3:** Mechanistic Pathways and endpoints for *in vitro* chemical testing. It provides a
 985 summary of key processes involved in neurotoxicity caused by different chemicals.

986 Abbreviations: LC3- Microtubule-associated protein 1 light chain 3, SQSTM1-
987 Sequestosome1, NF-H- Neurofilament heavy Chain, NF-L- Neurofilament Light Chain,
988 GABA- Gamma-Aminobutyric Acid, AMPA- α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-
989 isoxazolepropionic acid, ROS- Reactive Oxygen Species, MAP2- Microtubule-associated
990 protein 2, NO CGMP- Nitric Oxide Cyclic Guanosine Monophosphate, GSH-Glutathione,
991 LDH- Lactate dehydrogenase, T4- Tetra iodothyronine, T3- Triiodothyronine PKC- Protein
992 Kinase C, DNA- Deoxyribonucleic Acid
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996 **Figure 4:** *In vivo* studies for identifying chemicals induced neurotoxicity. It includes
997 different neurological endpoints, biomarkers and pathways for identifying toxicity.

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1001 **Figure 5:** End points, biomarkers and mechanistic pathways for *in vivo* neurotoxicity.
 1002 Behavioral assessment act as qualitative test for neuronal damage. Biomarkers, oxidative
 1003 stress, thyroid hormones, genetic expression (transcriptome) and immune system provide
 1004 mechanistic pathways for damage.

1005 Abbreviations: LTP- Long term potentiation, PKC- Protein Kinase C, TH- Thyroid Hormone,
 1006 AP1- Activator protein, Sp1 – Specificity protein, NF-KB – Nuclear factor Kappa-B, CREB-
 1007 Camp Responsive Element Modulator, LTP- Long term Potentiation, fEPSPs- Field
 1008 Excitatory Postsynaptic Potentials, Classical neurotransmitters - acetylcholine, glutamate, c-
 1009 aminobutyric acid, glycine, dopamine, norepinephrine, epinephrine, serotonin, aspartic acid,
 1010 and taurine, SOD- superoxide dismutase, 8-OH-dG- 8-hydroxy- 2-deoxyguanosine, DPC -
 1011 DNA-protein crosslinks, GFAP- glial fibrillary acidic protein, Caspase-3- cysteine-aspartic
 1012 acid protease 3, ROS- reactive oxygen species, DPC- DNA-protein crosslinks, TNF-a - tumor
 1013 necrosis factor alpha, IL-1β- interleukin-1 beta, Syn2a-synapsin Iia, Mbp- Myelin basic
 1014 protein, gap-43- growth associated protein 43, HPT- hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid.
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1018 **Figure 6:** Endpoints for epidemiological studies to assess impact of chemicals on human
 1019 nervous system. Body fluid concentration includes maternal cord and serum, urine, breast
 1020 milk and CSF fluid for detecting concertation of chemicals and metabolites inside human
 1021 body.

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1023 **Figure 7:** End-points and statistical tools for translating effect of chemicals to further assess
 1024 risk.

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1027 **Figure 8:** Integrated Translational approach for neuronal risk Assessment. This approach
 1028 consist of utilizing data from *in vitro*, *in vivo* and epidemiology studies to validate *in silico*
 1029 model. These model will further act as a tool for translation and prediction of risk to human
 1030 species.

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